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Transforming Libraries into Inclusive Spaces: The Paradigm and Functions of Living Collection in Academic Library of Indonesia

Objective. This research aims to understand the paradigm underlying the implementation of living collection services and the functions of living collection presented at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library. **Method.** This research uses qualitative methods, with collecting the data through observation, interviews, and documentation. The data that has been obtained is then analyzed by performing data reduction. After that, the data is presented in the form of text, images, and tables, followed by drawing conclusions related to the research questions. **Result.** The research results show that the living collection at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library refers to inclusive and knowledge management paradigm. The inclusive paradigm helps libraries strive for the dissemination of information to all users without exception, while the knowledge management paradigm allows libraries to manage and maintain rare information that can be accessed into the future. Living Collection as inclusive service present any functions namely educational, information, preservation, research, and recreational functions. **Conclusions.** By using an inclusive and knowledge management paradigm, living collections represent many functions that help libraries transforming new face to become inclusive-based libraries that can be enjoyed by all communities.

Keywords: academic library; inclusive library; living collection; library transformation

Introduction

Academic libraries have a very strategic role in supporting education and disseminating information to improve the quality of human resources. Information resources owned by higher education libraries are expected to be accepted and utilized by students, lecturers, and education personnel such as laboratory assistants, librarians, administrative staff, and others without distinguishing race, ethnicity, religion, skin color, or social status (Gupta, Liu, Lin, Zhong, & Suzuki, 2024). This equalization effort is related to the concept of inclusivity in libraries. This is to be done by libraries to be able to serve all types of users without distinction, so that the ideals of an inclusive-based library can be realized.

The concept of inclusive-based libraries has been heavily promoted in recent years. The International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) defines inclusive libraries as spaces that should be accessible and welcoming to all community members, regardless of their backgrounds, abilities, or circumstances (Beyene, Mekonnen, & Giannoumis, 2023). This concept advocates for libraries to function as safe and neutral spaces with equal opportunities to access information and engage in lifelong learning (Green, 2019). Thus, libraries must continue to strive to maximize services to all users and invite the public to be involved in library activities.

In supporting inclusivity, libraries can do various things, such as providing diverse collections, open access to information, and services that encourage equality of users (Algolaylat, Alodat, Muhidat, & Almakani, 2023). Thus, users can interact with the library and use the resources, services and spaces provided, positively impacting their achievement (Ronning, 2024). In addition, to ensure students' academic success, academic libraries can make systematic changes, such as changing library spaces to be more inclusive, diversifying collections, and providing

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diversity-based services that are appropriate to each academic environment (Wambui, Muigai, & Kamau, 2023).

Higher education institutions accept students from various backgrounds (Subramaniam & Jaeger, 2010). They also include students with disabilities in general classes (Ilako, Maceviciute, & Muwanguzi, 2020). This is a big challenge for libraries, which must be aware of students' differences and ensure that no student is left behind (Aminu & Perpetua, 2023). Despite the diversity of students, they are often still regarded as "different" and not served in the same way as the majority (Horsfall & Opara, 2023). This condition cannot be tolerated because it can lead to intolerance and a lack of respect for each other.

Indonesia is a pluralistic country with various differences inherent in society, such as ethnicity, race, culture and religion. Some universities in Indonesia accept students with various background differences, including students with disabilities. This is the case in one of the Islamic-based universities, but they also accept students with other religious backgrounds. Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University is an Islamic-based university that accepts students and lecturers from other religious backgrounds. Some students with disabilities are also accepted there. This is certainly a challenge and a great opportunity for the library to realize inclusion-based library services to adjust the institution's conditions. It is said that the evolution of academic libraries is linked to the evolution of their parent institutions, as the information services provided by libraries are uniquely linked to the specific needs of the educational and research communities at the University (Ngulube, 2022).

The library of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University is one of the inclusive libraries in Indonesia. This is because there are quite a lot of disabled students accepted by the campus so that the library provides several inclusive services such as the disabled corner and also the living collection. The living collection is a library information service in the form of humans that can provide information to users. This concept is inspired by the human library program but is not directly affiliated with the human library in Denmark. The living collection has little in common with the concept of a human library where users can access information by borrowing humans and having direct dialogue with those who act as collections. The human library also focuses on themes that represent groups in our society who often experience prejudice, stigmatization or discrimination due to lifestyle, diagnosis, beliefs, disabilities, social status, ethnic origin, etc (Human Library, 2024). However, the living collection itself has a difference where the themes raised are also related to the characteristics of Indonesia, namely religious and racial or ethnic diversity (<https://lib.uin-suka.ac.id/>).

The term living collection has long been around, but its context is not related to libraries. This term is often used in collections of living plants. Then this term is used in a broader context according to the definition given namely as usercentric innovation environments (Eskelinen et al., 2015), in which creators, managers, and users can participate in co-creating innovations that enable social and economic impact (McPhee, Leminen, Schuurman, Westerlund, & Huizingh, 2018). If we relate to libraries, then the term living collection can be used to describe the participation between libraries and the community to collaborate together in presenting information.

Living collection at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library as an inclusion-based service has a major role in providing equal access to information for users. There has been no research that specifically examines the philosophical basis for implementing living collection in libraries. Therefore, it is important to examine the paradigm used in implementing living collection and what functions are obtained to help libraries transform into inclusion-based libraries. This research is expected to provide an understanding of the living collection paradigm that can be applied in libraries to realize inclusive library services.

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Research Question. Academic libraries have a responsibility to provide services that can be accessed and utilized by the entire campus community. To meet this need, libraries need to transform into inclusive services that are able to accommodate various user backgrounds, preferences and information needs. Given the importance of this transformation, this research focuses on questions that will explore the philosophical foundations of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library in providing living collection as an inclusive service. Therefore, the formulation of the problem to be achieved is as follows:

RQ1: What Paradigm is built in the Living Collection as a form of inclusive library transformation in Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library?

RQ 2: What are the functions of the Living Collection to support the inclusive service in Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library?

Methods

This research used a qualitative approach to understand specific issues, problems, or events (Creswell, 2015). This method provides an in-depth description and explanation regarding the application of living collection as an inclusion service in the Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library. Data were collected through observation, documentation, and interviews.

Observation is done by following the process of users' access to the Living Collection. Documentation is done by accessing documents owned by Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library related to the Living Collection, such as the annual report of the Living Collection service, the Consent Form to be part of the Living Collection, and the user publication permit. Semi-formal interviews were conducted in this study with several resource persons who deeply understand the living collection. The determination of informants was carried out by purposive sampling involving 6 people, namely 2 people from the head and development team of the Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library as the initiators, 2 people from the librarian as the coordinator and team of living collection activities as field implementers, and 2 people from the person who became the living collection as a knowledge provider for users. The informants were sufficient because they represented each part of the parties involved in the Living Collection of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library.

Data analysis was carried out by reducing, presenting data, and drawing conclusions (Creswell, 2015). Data was reduced by selecting, classifying, and adjusting to the research focus. Data presentation was carried out in tables, which were then narrated. The conclusion was drawn by interpreting the data compiled in the previous stage. The research was considered complete when the results of the analysis process had clear validity through triangulation and member check.

Result and Discussion

a. Result

1. *The Paradigm of Living Collection*

Living Collection of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library presents collection services in human form as an innovative effort to develop library services. The Living Collection was launched in 2021. The purpose of the Living Collection is to promote inclusive values to the academic community of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University which will change views on existing differences, as well as preserve rare knowledge in society so that it can be used in the future. The central issue raised by the Living Collection of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University

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library is focused on two main aspects namely (1) inclusiveness and (2) management of unique knowledge owned by individuals.

“Living Collection is a combination of inclusion and knowledge management. If inclusion is related to inequality, then knowledge management is added by having people who have knowledge but have not written it down” (Labibah, Isrowiyanti, and Marwiyah, March & April, 2024).

The inclusive aspect applied relates to creating inclusive spaces as a service for minority or marginalized communities. The management of unique knowledge is done by conveying and storing knowledge that is still tacit knowledge that many people do not know yet. These issues were chosen to create harmony and diversity in the campus environment and the general public. In addition, through this activity, the library has disseminated information and insights on understanding inclusion for students.

Fig. 1. Living Collection Paradigm
Source: Data by researchers, 2024

An inclusive framework, the Living Collection seeks to collect and share narratives from diverse minority voices, whether they have faced discrimination or stigma or lived differently from the majority of society. The resource persons of Living Collection do not need to be victims of discrimination in order to share their knowledge.

“I have never felt discriminated against, even though I am a minority in this institution” (interview with Abdurrahman, April 2024). “To do even small things, I have been discriminated against” (interview with Arif, April 2024).

The goal is to share knowledge and experiences to foster a deeper and more empathetic understanding among users. Through these interactions, the Living Collection offers a space where

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underrepresented groups can share their stories, enriching the academic community's understanding of diversity and inclusion. The initiative empowers the academic community by facilitating two-way communication between users and interviewees, who recount their experiences as members of minority groups. Although inclusive in scope, Living Collection cannot include minorities in their entirety, aside from limited human resources, there are also societal norms, boundaries, and cultures that should not be violated. So the themes presented will be adjusted to the needs and desires of the academic community by considering the limits of norms, religion, state, and customs in society.

In the implementation, users, who usually come from majority backgrounds, have the opportunity to harmonize and broaden their perspectives by hearing the stories of minority experiences first-hand. They can freely explore and ask questions about the topics raised during these sessions, encouraging greater openness to different dimensions of human experience in a diverse academic environment. This exchange helps develop an inclusive mindset that appreciates and respects each individual's unique challenges and strengths.

Within the knowledge management framework, the library, through the Living Collection, seeks to manage, store, and distribute the unique knowledge possessed by each individual that may rarely be found in written documents. The Living Collection specifically features speakers who bring experiences and insights that are not only valuable but also rare. This dynamic and evolving knowledge over time often includes perspectives and expertise that have not been formally documented, so this collection fills a gap in the existing literature.

“So if it's Knowledge Management, so maybe the thinking is just tacit, tacit knowledge has not been made explicit” (interview with Labibah and Sri Astuti, April 2024).

The Living Collection enables the process of making tacit knowledge explicit through interaction with its primary source. This process involves a dialog between the reader and the collection, where individuals who act as living books share their experiences, insights, and knowledge directly with the user. Through this dialog, previously implicit knowledge can be expressed, documented and disseminated.

This process is accomplished by providing direct access to readers through two-way interactions with the resource person, allowing for a more in-depth transfer of knowledge. The Living Collection also documents these interactions (with consent) as a form of ongoing conservation. Through this strategy, the library not only passively provides knowledge but also ensures that unique information is kept alive and accessible across generations.

In the realization, the library brings in resource persons from several minorities around the Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University environment. In 2024, Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library has 5 topics related to inclusive issues, namely Lecture with Disability, Catholic Religious (Nun) from Student, Chinese Community/Ethnic, Arabian Community, Student with Disabilities and 5 topics from a person's unique knowledge and experience, namely Pluralism Concept, Humanitarian Activists and Organ Donors, Batik Rajah, Indigenous Belief / Religion, and Parenting Children with Disabilities. The following are examples of Living Collection access carried out by users, while opening up inclusive spaces and preserving knowledge:

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Fig. 2. Offline Access of Living Collection (Student with Disabilities)

Fig. 3. Online Access of Living Collection (Arabian Community)

Source: Data of Observation by researchers, 2024

From the explanation, it can be said, the living collection at the Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library relies on two (2) paradigms, they are paradigm inclusivity and knowledge management. On the paradigm of inclusivity that allows various groups to benefit from dynamic and relevant library collections. By implementing the principle of inclusivity, the library seeks to create a collaborative space where knowledge can be accessed and developed together by all members of the academic community, regardless of background or discipline. This is in line with the main purpose of the library as a learning center that encourages active involvement of users in utilizing diverse collections, thereby enriching the learning experience and strengthening social ties in the campus environment.

In addition, this program integrates the knowledge management paradigm as an effort to optimize the management of information and knowledge. Through this strategy, the library not only collects and stores information, but also organizes and distributes it effectively to users. Thus, the library plays an active role in the knowledge cycle, from acquisition, management, to dissemination, all of which are directed to support intellectual growth and innovation among academics. The integration of inclusivity and knowledge management ensures that the living collection program can continue to grow along with user needs, making it an adaptive and future-oriented library service model.

2. *The Functions of Living Collection in Library*

Living Collection is present as part of the service in the academic library. Living Collection is involved in realizing the library's function and supporting the success of the institution's vision and mission through the library as an integral institution in the implementation of higher education. This affects the use of built-in central issues, namely inclusiveness and unique knowledge, which then underlies the functionality offered to users.

Based on the results of interviews with informants, the library, through the Living Collection, strives to present functions in accordance with the functions of an academic library. As an innovation in the library collection, it usually includes print and non-print collections (Yulia & Sujana, 2014) into human-form collections. The Living Collection is present as a new collection in the library, presenting functions in accordance with the functions of an academic library, which include education, information, preservation, research and recreation (Qalyubi et al., 2003).

The Living Collection creates educational media through a collection of people who provide knowledge needs related to inclusivity. The resource person directly transfers knowledge

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to library users by conducting an interactive dialogue between the user and the main source, thus creating two-way communication that effectively presents the process of providing knowledge.

From the perspective of the information function, the library, through the Living Collection, provides information that can help users understand complex social and cultural realities and raise their awareness of issues that may go unnoticed in written sources. The resource person of the Living Collection conveys information about the experience of being a minority in a diverse society.

The library's preservation function through the Living Collection ensures that these resource person valuable knowledge and experiences are not lost. By documenting the interactive dialogue between patrons and Living Collection characters, the library is able to store and preserve information for future generations. This allows the library to build a living archive that reflects diversity and inclusivity in society.

In addition, the Living Collection also contributes to the library's research and recreation functions. As an innovation in the scope of academic libraries in Indonesia, raising issues of diversity, social inclusion, and unique knowledge not owned by most of society, the Living Collection opens opportunities for users to research related matters. In addition, accessing the Living Collection through dialogue allows for cultural recreation by accessing collections that match readers' interests and bring up new ideas useful for developing users' creativity and imagination.

Table 1

The Functions of Living Collection in Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library

No	Aspects	Functions
1	Education	The Living Collection addresses knowledge needs related to inclusivity through existing figures, transferring knowledge directly to users through interactive dialogues.
2	Information	The Living Collection provides information to help users understand complex social and cultural realities and increase their awareness of inclusive issues.
3	Preservation	The Living Collection ensures that these resource persons' valuable, inclusive knowledge and experiences are not lost to be used for future generations.
4	Research	As an innovation in the scope of academic libraries in Indonesia, the Living Collection allows users to research inclusion and diversity.
5	Recreation	Accessing the Living Collection by engaging in dialogue with inclusive figures allows for cultural recreation.

Source: Data by Researchers, 2024

In presenting an inclusive environment in academic libraries, libraries can provide physical facilities for minorities, especially for people with disabilities, in meeting their academic needs.

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Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library provides a disabled corner, braille books, and the use of sign language in the library. The provision of these facilities is commonplace in academic libraries in Indonesia. However, the Living Collection produces a new transformation of inclusive space in academic libraries in Indonesia. The main target of this service is not only for those from minority groups to experience an inclusive environment but also for academic groups, in general, to create an equal institutional environment by understanding each other.

The transformation that occurs in inclusive spaces in libraries is a change in services that are only oriented towards making it easier for someone to access the needs in the library with their shortcomings, to providing access to everyone to understand each other's differences and shortcomings so that they can help each other to create easy access to the needs in the library. Through direct dialog with minorities, the majority group can understand their point of view, thus creating a balanced understanding.

The Living Collection seeks to build awareness of the campus academic community to appreciate the existing differences and diversity. Through the Living Collection, the library tries to create a sense of mutual respect among members of the campus community so that this difference does not become a barrier for someone to be able to carry out academic activities on campus. The Living Collection is a bridge to understanding the values of inclusiveness and diversity better, strengthening a sense of unity and togetherness, and creating an equal campus environment.

In realizing this role under the needs and conditions of the campus community, Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library takes the resource persons who are still members of the academic community of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University into the Living Collection. The library presents themes connected to the reality of minorities on the Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University library campus. The Living Collection includes themes on diversity, disability, and ethnicity. This shows that the library, through the Living Collection, tries to actively participate in implementing inclusive education on campus. Thus, the Living Collection is expected to be an effective educational tool for shaping the character and inclusive values of the academic community of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University.

b. Discussion

The Living Collection at the Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library not only has functions as an innovation in library collections, but also as a driver of inclusivity and knowledge management in the academic environment. The existence of the Living Collection proves that libraries can expand their role from merely providing information resources to facilitators of in-depth dialogue and interaction. This allows for direct knowledge transfer between resource persons and users through a two-way approach, which is effective in connecting theory with real practice.

Another important point is the information and preservation function offered by the Living Collection. The library plays a role in providing relevant information related to diversity and social reality, which may not be fully presented in written collections. This approach emphasizes the importance of collective memory and the preservation of minority experiences as part of a living archive. This shows that the Living Collection is not only a means of education, but also supports research, which can inspire creativity and enrich academic understanding.

In this analysis, it is seen that libraries have a strategic role in building an inclusive space where all members of the community can feel valued and understood. By facilitating interactive dialogue between majority and minority groups, the Living Collection seeks to create a more balanced understanding and creating an equal academic environment. This effort directly supports

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the goal of inclusive education and fosters collective awareness of the importance of diversity and mutual respect in the campus environment.

Conclusions

The conclusion of this research shows that the Living Collection at the Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library uses two paradigms, namely inclusiveness and knowledge management. It plays a role beyond just innovation in library services, but this program supports inclusivity and knowledge management by facilitating effective interactive dialogue between users and resource persons. Through a two-way approach, the Living Collection connects theory with practice, enriching library functions including education, information, preservation, research, and also recreation. The Living Collection not only enriches traditional library services but also affirms the library's commitment to the values of inclusivity and diversity. By presenting human resources as part of the collection, this program provides opportunities for all members of the academic community to understand different perspectives, deepen empathy, and encourage collaboration. This innovation positions the library as a center for active learning and intercultural dialogue, which is very relevant in creating a supportive and inclusive academic environment. Thus, the Living Collection becomes an important element in creating an inclusive space in the library and supporting inclusive education at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University Library.

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Перетворення бібліотек на інклюзивні простори: парадигма та функції Живої бібліотеки в академічній бібліотеці Індонезії

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Мета. Це дослідження має на меті зрозуміти парадигму, що лежить в основі впровадження послуг Живих бібліотек, а також функції Живих бібліотек, представлених у бібліотеці Державного ісламського університету ім. Сунана Каліджаги. **Методика.** Це дослідження використовує якісні методи зі збором даних через спостереження, інтерв'ю та документацію. Отримані дані потім аналізуються шляхом їх скорочення та представлення у вигляді тексту, зображень і таблиць, з подальшим формулюванням висновків, пов'язаних із питаннями дослідження. **Результати** дослідження показують, що Жива бібліотека Державного ісламського університету імені Сунана Каліджаги відноситься до інклюзивної парадигми та парадигми управління знаннями. Інклюзивна парадигма допомагає бібліотекам прагнути до поширення інформації для всіх користувачів без винятку, тоді як парадигма управління знаннями дозволяє бібліотекам управляти й зберігати рідкісну інформацію, до якої можна отримати доступ у майбутньому. Жива бібліотека як інклюзивна послуга виконує декілька функцій, а саме: освітню, інформаційну, збереження, дослідницьку та рекреаційну. **Висновки.** Використовуючи інклюзивну парадигму та парадигму управління знаннями, Живі бібліотеки виконують багато функцій, котрі допомагають бібліотекам трансформувати нове обличчя та ставати інклюзивними бібліотеками, якими можуть користуватися всі спільноти.

Ключові слова: академічна бібліотека; інклюзивна бібліотека; Жива бібліотека; трансформація бібліотеки

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